

Modular designs at the Early Byzantine pilgrimage site of Philoxenite, Egypt

Abstract:

New research at the Philoxenite site in northern Egypt has identified six large building complexes, each based on a modular design. Each building is composed of replicated segments and dates to the 6th century CE. This approach to design, used at Philoxenite, was not seen elsewhere on such a scale at that time. Nevertheless, modular design was deeply rooted in the construction traditions of the Roman and Early Byzantine periods, when it was used primarily for shops, warehouses and cisterns. In Philoxenite, it was used to erect a town district that catered to the needs of pilgrims heading from Alexandria to Abū Mīnā, the largest Christian sanctuary at the time.

Keywords: Early Byzantine period, Philoxenite, modular buildings, pilgrimage, Egypt, St Menas sanctuary

Introduction

The design methods used for churches constructed during the Early Byzantine period (between the 4th century and the first half of the 7th century) are very well researched. They involved using sets of proportions based on descriptive architecture and accompanied by drawn plans and field sketches.¹ Much less is known about the methods used to design secular buildings.

Excavations and surveys at Philoxenite (near Alexandria, Egypt) help expand our knowledge

¹ Chen 1990, 523–33; Wilkinson 1984, 116–23; Wilkinson 1981, 156–72; Spremo-Petrović 1971; Junecke 1983; Milson 2007, p. 243–72. Detailed information on the work of specialists involved in design and construction of buildings in the Early Byzantine period are available in Zanini 2007, 381–401; Papaconstantinou 2007, p. 31–46. Findings on later periods are also available in Ousterhout 1999, 58–85. Pre-existing plans for churches and marking them on the ground are described in Vita Porphyrii 75, 78; Vit Euthymii 24.

in this area. Research at the site has indicated that replicated plans were used on a mass scale in buildings erected no earlier than the mid-6th century CE.² Philoxenite was the largest settlement that catered for the needs of pilgrims heading to the shrine of Saint Menas in Abū Mīnā. The large-scale use of modular design found at the site aided in urban planning, and today it helps us reconstruct the way the entire district was constructed in order to serve the needs of pilgrims. Philoxenite thus yields new insight into the influence of Christianity on Late Antiquity urban planning and the way that new cities were formed.³ This paper describes the method used to design the structures in this location and places it in the wider context of ancient traditions. Shops, warehouses and cisterns from Roman and Early Byzantine cities are used as comparative material. Contrasting the structures at Philoxenite with findings from other Christian pilgrimage sites helps reveal its unique nature.

Early Byzantine Philoxenite was an entirely new Christian settlement on the southern shores of Lake Mareotis.⁴ The settlement provided accommodation to pilgrims heading from Alexandria, located 21 km away, to the great shrine of St Menas, 17 km to the south. Thanks to the Encomium on Saint Menas, we know that construction at the site began during the reign of Emperor Justinian.⁵ This is confirmed by the discovery of imported fine ware pottery in the foundation layers, placing the site's golden age at no earlier than the mid-6th century CE.⁶

The construction project covered an area of approximately 11 ha and involved the erection of churches, a monumental street (St2) with adjoining buildings, and waterfronts with boardwalks

² Although the terms 'modular design' or 'modular buildings' are not found in Roman or Early Byzantine texts, the concept of monads – units which can be combined into a larger whole – was known in those times. This issue is discussed in the context of building design in the Early Byzantine period in Stewart 2015, 19–20, with further references.

³ For more on the changes in the form of Early Byzantine cities in comparison to the Roman period, see Lavan 2020; Blömer 2021. Both with extensive further references.

⁴ For years, Philoxenite was thought to be the same as the much older town of Marea, but this interpretation has not stood the test of time. A summary of the discussion on the identification of Philoxenite is available in Derda 2020, 61–63.

⁵ Apa Mena, 147–48.

⁶ Derda et al. 2020, 561–565; Gwiazda and Derda 2021, 2–4.

and piers. This set of structures was complemented by several public latrines, a mill and two bath complexes.⁷ The buildings in this town were not built on an orthogonal plan; the streets run in straight lines and their arrangement is directly linked to the layout of monumental buildings (Fig. 1).

Although excavations at Philoxenite first began in the late 1970s, our understanding of the form and principles behind local urban development is still limited. A new chapter in research was opened between 2018 and 2021, when the previous practice of uncovering entire buildings was abandoned, switching instead to doing extensive surveys with test pits. The range of methods used during fieldwork was also expanded. These included non-invasive magnetic surveys combined with the creation of digital surface models using RTK.⁸ Such methods were able to capture the extent of the dense development of the town and located numerous, previously unknown buildings. The work was also accompanied by an architectural survey, which involved sketching the wall tops visible on the surface of excavations using total stations. An orthophoto plan of the entire site was also created using a UAV, allowing all visible structures to be mapped, including those excavated by other archaeological teams. Orthophotos taken with a camera suspended from a 5 m aerial photography pole were used to document the buildings and their individual parts in more detail. In individual cases, building plans created using this varied documentation were verified and refined through small-scale archaeological test trenches. With these excavations, not only could the positions of the walls be verified, but the dates of their foundation and alterations could also be determined. Thanks to this approach, it was possible to identify and analyse several buildings based on repetitive modules.

⁷ Szymańska and Babraj 2008; Gwiazda and Derda 2021, 2–8; Gwiazda and Wielgosz-Rondolino 2019, 264–67; Haggag 2010, 49–52.

⁸ Derda et al. 2021, 123–36.

Modular buildings in Philoxenite

All the modular buildings in Philoxenite are located in the northern part of the site, near the shore of the lake, and cover an area of nearly 5 ha, constituting almost half of the urban area (Fig. 1). The south-western part of the town was designed differently. An orthogonal arrangement of rectangular and trapezoidal insulae was found at the southern end of the settlement. Buildings constructed on varying plans were identified in each insula. The same was true of other buildings located between the insula quarter and bath complex T2. This is where the largest natural elevated terrain in the site area is located, and where walls were discovered that do not form an ordered urban grid – in contrast to neighbouring parts of the town. At first glance, this apparently chaotic arrangement of buildings results from the diverse terrain in this part of the site. No modular buildings were found in this area.

Based on these observations, we conclude that at least three approaches to urban planning were used in Philoxenite. Modular buildings were constructed only in the northern part of the town. The modular design enabled the creation of a diverse range of building plans, which were then replicated when erecting large-scale architectural projects. The term ‘modular buildings’ refers to the method by which they were designed rather than their function, which in most cases is ambiguous and will be discussed later in the article.

Building S3

Building S3 was located in the north-eastern part of the site, behind the apse of the Great Basilica.⁹ The walls of this structure, as well as other structures described below, were erected using limestone pseudo-ashlars, laid in an *opus isodomum* course and bonded with a large

⁹ Information about the survey of building S3 and the test trenches in the area is available in: Kościuk 2012, 32–34, Babraj, Drzymuchowska, and Willburger 2014, 48–51; Derda et al. 2020, 535–36, 538–41.

amount of mortar.¹⁰ The floors that we were able to identify in these buildings were made of mortar or limestone slabs. Building S3 is rectangular and had a portico on the north side leading to an independent wing (Fig. 2). The central and southern sections contained four additional independent units, each with a separate staircase leading to the second floor. The two units on the west side are a mirror image of those on the east side. Each of these four sections is divided into two rows of rooms. The rooms on the front side are smaller than the rooms located deeper inside the building. Notably, the modules located in the central and southern parts have the same shape, though in different proportions. Differences between the western and eastern façades were also identified. As for the western side, the building appears to have been preceded by a portico, the stylobate of which was located in one of the test trenches.¹¹ No trace of a similar structure was found on the eastern side, which leads us to believe that entrances to the building from that side were directly adjacent to the street. All of the above-described parts of building S3 were erected as part of a single project, although some of the walls are tied to later modifications.

Buildings in area W1

On the eastern side of the site, a waterfront wall with a length of at least 230 m was discovered, with four additional urban development components identified on its western side: 1. A cornice; 2. Three modular buildings (W1-A, B and C); 3. A monumental street (St2); and 4. Another three modular buildings (W5-A, B and C). The individual modular buildings in area W1 were separated from each other by narrow streets running along the east–west axis, and their outlines took the form of elongated rectangles. The exception is W1-A, with an oblique southern end. This shape was due to the fact that the structure had to be adapted to the SQ1

¹⁰ The term ‘pseudo-ashlars’ was coined by German architects working in nearby Abū Mīnā. It refers to stones cut into shapes that resemble cuboids. However, the local limestone was so brittle that it was rare for such blocks to have distinguishable edges and corners.

¹¹ Information on the structure that has now been identified as a stylobate is available in Derda, Gwiazda, and Pawlikowska-Gwiazda 2020, 535, fig. 2.

saqiya (water wheel) located on that side.¹² Buildings W1-A, B and C consisted of four elements (Fig. 3). Porticoes with square supports, identified on the surface of the site at regular intervals, were found on the eastern façades of the buildings. Behind them were rows of rectangular rooms reminiscent of typical Roman and Early Byzantine shops. Units comprising a larger and a smaller room, terminating in another portico that formed part of the monumental street (St2), were located at the backs of these ‘shops’. One of test trenches uncovered a part of this portico with a limestone socle resting on a stylobate.

No installations or artefact assemblages were discovered during excavations in the area of buildings W1-A and W1-B that could be used to identify their original functions. This is due to the fact that people have long settled in this area and to the structural modifications that took place during the Early Islamic period (the second half of the 7th century and the first half of the 8th century CE). In this later phase, these buildings were adapted to the needs of their new residents. This included adding smaller units to the buildings, closing up the porticoes and adding rooms on the east side. A different type of building material, crushed limestone, was used in these alterations, which makes it easier to distinguish between the Early Byzantine and Early Islamic phases.¹³

The analysis of orthophoto plans of buildings W1-A, B and C – verified by the test trenches – identified recurring modules inside the structures. Each consisted of three cellular rooms on the east side and two on the west side (Fig. 3). Each of these units had a square layout, each side being 10.2 m long. Eight such layouts were found to have been replicated inside building W1-B and at least eight within W1-A. Due to the fact that a large part of building W1-C was covered by the earth excavated during our work, only two modules could be identified.

¹² Additional information on saqiya Sq1 is available in Babraj and Szymańska 2008, 85–101.

¹³ For more on the Early Islamic alterations, see Derda et al. 2020, 568–69.

Buildings in area W5

No excavations were carried out in the complex comprising buildings W5-A, B and C, located on the west side of the monumental street (St2). Nevertheless, based on orthophotos of the surface, it was possible to deduce that the buildings were designed using a method similar to that described above (Fig. 3). Base squares with dimensions of 8.7 m were used in the design of these structures. The modular units were found on both the western and eastern sides of each of the three buildings identified here. The presence of columnar porticoes on the north–south axis has not been confirmed in this case. However, it seems likely that they would be there, primarily on the side facing the town’s main street (St2). Porticoes on both sides of this thoroughfare would have formed a columnar street, which was one of the more characteristic elements of Eastern Mediterranean urban planning.¹⁴

Buildings in areas W2 and W4

Another two complexes of modular buildings (W2 and W4) were located immediately adjacent to the western waterfront and flanked the double bath complex T2 to the west and east. Much of building W2 was excavated in the 1970s by an Egyptian team led by F. el-Fakharany.¹⁵ They were able to create the first idealised plan of one of these buildings, which suggested that it was laid out on a rectangular plan. Orthophotos taken at the site helped verify this hypothesis and showed that building W2 was in fact built on a plan that resembled a trapezoid (Fig. 4). This was due to the builders’ intention to adapt the eastern part of this building to the different urban grid on the eastern side (Fig. 1).

The Egyptian team believed that the building was used as workshops. This hypothesis was most likely based on the discovery of a kiln made of bricks in one of the rooms on the east side.

¹⁴ A similar arrangement is attested in the neighbouring sanctuary at Abū Mīnā: Grossmann 1990, 43–47. For more information on monumental streets in Early Byzantine cities, see L. Lavan 2020, 34–61.

¹⁵ Haggag 2010, 50.

However, it cannot be ruled out that this installation was a later addition as part of modification works similar to those identified in building W1-B. Reports from excavations do not describe any other objects discovered in building W2 which could assist in determining its original function.

From the side of the lake and from the west, building W2 was boundaried by a cornice and adjoined a street that ran perpendicular to it. Running parallel to these was a stylobate with pillars that marked the course of two porticoes (north and west). An architectural module that was replicated four times within the structure could be seen among the rooms located behind the stylobate. On the north side of the building was a large space flanked by two elongated rooms. The same layout was also used in the south wing, only mirrored. Several additional partition walls were erected there, creating smaller rooms and staircases.

Building W4, located on the west side of bath complex T2, has never been excavated. However, based on the layout of walls visible on the surface of the site, we can infer that this structure had a layout similar to that of W2. One difference was that it was rectangular in shape, due to the orthogonal layout of neighbouring buildings and streets.

Bath complex T2

A double thermal bath complex was located between buildings W2 and W4. The northern part, which featured frigidaria (Fig. 4), had previously been excavated by an Egyptian team.¹⁶ This part of the bath complex was built from limestone pseudo-dimension stones, while the unexcavated caldaria located on the south side were mostly constructed from baked bricks.¹⁷ The layout of frigidaria in bath complex T2 is identical to that of the Great Bath at Abū Mīnā, built during the reign of Justinian.¹⁸ The bath complex at Philoxenite differ from the original in

¹⁶ Sadek 1992, 549–54.

¹⁷ Detailed locations of the caldarium based on magnetic survey results is discussed in: Derda et al. 2021, 132.

¹⁸ Müller-Wiener 1966, 173–80, fig. 1–3.

that it featured two frigidaria that were exact copies of each other. The existence of dual facilities most likely stems from the Late Antiquity practice of separating men and women in public buildings, and such has also been found in other bath complexes in the Mareotis region.¹⁹

Area DDI

The use of mirrored plans was also identified to the west of the dense urban area. A building referred to by various researchers as a dry dock can be found here.²⁰ This interpretation is questionable and could not be confirmed from the verification works done in this area. What was possible to identify in this location were two walls that continued into the water of the lake; the southern extension of these walls forms a channel that separates two identical wings of a building (Fig. 5). Each building consisted of four rows of rooms, where the remains of limestone slab floors were discovered. The identified wall remnants were erected with limestone pseudo-ashlars in an *opus isodomum* arrangement.

Modular design in Roman and Early Byzantine cities

Cellular shops, which became widespread in the Mediterranean region starting in the 2nd century BCE, are an excellent example of modular design.²¹ They were usually constructed along streets in combination with columnar porticoes, or on public squares and in macella (Fig. 6a and 6b).²² They may have consisted of a single room with an entrance on the street, although there were often additional compartments in the back. They were erected in clusters of several to a dozen or so units, with the rooms at the front of the building usually of identical size.

¹⁹ For information on double bath complexes in the Mareotis region and the separation of spaces for men and women, see Fournet and Redon 2017, 307–09; Derda et al. 2020, 545.

²⁰ More information about this building is provided in: Petruso and Gabel 1982, 11–12; Kingsley 2004, 153.

²¹ Ellis 2018, 127–47.

²² An overview of Roman macella, including those featuring replicated rooms can be found in: De Ruyt 1983, 301–3. For more information on Early Byzantine commercial buildings, which included cellular shops, see Lavan 2020, 381–91.

Buildings of this type were erected exclusively in urban settlements until the Early Islamic period. This type of cellular room can be found in the eastern parts of buildings W1-A, B and C in Philoxenite. However, identifying these rooms as shops beyond all doubt would be unjustified, as there is no available information regarding their original furnishings.²³

The concept of a replicated module was also used in the design of storerooms and water cisterns.²⁴ Granaries were often created by combining several large rectangular rooms with independent entrances.²⁵ In Classe, a port near Ravenna, at least 18 unconnected warehouses with identical layouts were erected in the early 5th century CE. They were arranged in an orderly fashion along canals and the street, which indicates that their construction was part of a wider project.²⁶ Some of these buildings consisted of the warehouse space proper, built on a square plan and flanked by porticoes on two sides, similarly to structures found in area W1 in Philoxenite. This structure's function was identified based on the huge number of amphorae imported from other regions of the Mediterranean that were found there.

Monumental cisterns, which were designed as a combination of multiple square or rectangular modules separated by pillars or columns (Fig. 6c), constitute the final similarity between the site and other Roman and Early Byzantine settlements. Similar structures can be found in locations such as Early Byzantine Alexandria, near Philoxenite.²⁷ As noted by C.A. Stewart, the use of modular design in the construction of cisterns and granaries enabled architects to

²³ On adopting a cautious approach in identifying the original purpose of such cellular rooms: Allison 2001, 186–88.

²⁴ Such building design is observed also in military barracks. For the review of Roman period barracks see: Davison 1989, 209–216. Modular design of fortification is discussed in: Oleson 2017, 237–261, with further references.

²⁵ The most complete overview of granaries and warehouses from the Roman period is provided in: Rickman 1971, 19–22, 41–53, 137–40. See also the corridor warehouse complex in Early Byzantine Caesarea Maritima (Patrich 1996, 156–60, fig. 1) and Roman granaries of Karanis (Husselman 1979, 56–62, plan 18–19).

²⁶ Augenti 2011, 18, 26–27; Augenti and Cirelli 2012, 208–12.

²⁷ Rodziewicz 1984, 27, 61, 263, 266, plan I; Crow 2020, 114–22.

visualise and estimate the capacity of such structures at a theoretical level and adapt it to suit peoples' needs.²⁸

Early Byzantine pilgrimage infrastructure in the Mediterranean

In the context of the specific function of Philoxenite, we should also examine the secular buildings associated with Christian pilgrimage sites. Understandably, archaeological research in such locations has often focused on uncovering churches. The Isaurian shrine of St Thekla in Meriamlik, enlarged in the 5th century by Emperor Zeno, is a good example of such a site. The structures identified in this area primarily include several churches, with a bath complex and a large number of cisterns.²⁹ However, we do not know what was located in the spaces between these structures.

We have slightly more extensive knowledge of the sanctuary of St Simeon Stylites the Elder in northern Syria, which underwent development after Simeon's death in the second half of the 5th century CE. Some 30 rectangular buildings were identified on both sides of the processional road leading to the sanctuary, each of which was identical in form, according to D. Pieri. However, excavations have taken place in only two of these buildings, which is insufficient to confirm whether these structures were, in fact, uniformly designed. Nevertheless, this archaeological work helped establish that two of these buildings were used as shops in the 6th and early 7th centuries.³⁰

²⁸ Detailed discussion of modular cisterns in the Early Byzantine period can be found in: Stewart 2015, 15–18. See also an example of a cistern found in Resafa (Sergiopolis) in Hof 2019, 225–28, fig. 4. Examples of Roman modular cisterns can be found in Döring 2007, 15, 45, 64, fig. 11, 36, 55.

²⁹ Kristensen 2017, 233–37, fig. 13.2.

³⁰ Pieri 2009, 1397–406.

Thanks to an inscription in Greek, two inns (*pandocheia*) for pilgrims were identified in the village of Deir Sem'an (Telanissos), located at the foot of the mountain where St. Simeon was venerated. Both were erected in 479 and were identical in form. The inns were two-storey buildings built on an elongated rectangular plan, surrounded by porticoes (Fig. 6d). The interiors of the buildings were divided into three rooms, with some of the space being used as stables. These buildings were adjacent to a monastery with a chapel.³¹ The fact the structures were erected in the same year, they had the same shape and their porticoes were partially interconnected, suggests that they were built as part of a single project, based on a duplicated design.

A building which J. Christern believes served as a hostel for pilgrims was located in the sanctuary of St Crispin's in Tebessa, Algeria. The hostel had an elongated rectangular shape and its interior was divided into three parts (Fig. 6e). The central part contained a spacious room with pillars, flanked by two rows of cellular rooms with mangers. The rooms for the pilgrims themselves were located upstairs.³²

More similar modular structures can be found among the uncovered remains of the Abū Mīnā sanctuary. Numerous cellular rooms were identified along the monumental street leading up to the tomb of St Menas (Fig. 6a). Each room had the same dimensions and was fronted by a portico.³³ Taken together, they formed a straight section of a larger building that was certainly erected as part of a single construction project. They were identified as shops based on their form, although there is no archaeological evidence to support this assumption. There were

³¹ The description of these buildings and other similar structures in the region is provided in: Butler 1920, 270, fig. 284; Tchalenko 1953, 208–9. The inscriptions associated with these inns were published in Prentice 1922, 169–70, 172–73, ins nos 1154 and 1155.

³² Christern 1976, 222–43.

³³ Grossmann and Kościuk 2005, 33–35, fig. 3.

certainly many more similar units along the monumental street in the sanctuary, but a large portion of the site has not been fully uncovered.

Cellular rooms have also been discovered in a semi-circular building located on the south side of the Basilica with St Menas' grave. The building also featured latrines, a portico and stairways leading upstairs.³⁴ Although the layout of this structure does not include identical modules, a mirrored set of several rooms is evident in its south-eastern part. It is believed that the building was certainly erected for the use of pilgrims, although there is no archaeological evidence that would allow its exact function to be pinpointed.

Mirror reflections were also used in the design of the west wing of the Great Peristyle Building. Its components include two peristyles separated by a corridor and two rows of rooms separating this part of the building from another peristyle on the eastern side.³⁵ This building is theorised to have been used as an overnight shelter for pilgrims. However, this theory is only speculative and based on the purpose of the site as a whole.

The uniqueness of Philoxenite

A summary of this review of modular buildings found in Mediterranean cities and secular structures found at pilgrimage sites yields two observations. Firstly, in terms of their architectural concept, which involved replicating components to form a larger whole, buildings discovered in the northern district of Philoxenite are part of a strongly rooted building tradition of the Roman and Early Byzantine periods. Despite this replication in their design, the buildings identified in Philoxenite are original in their layout, and no exact counterparts have been found at other sites. Moreover, no other locations have been discovered where modular design was

³⁴ Grossmann 1998, 289, fig. 8.

³⁵ Grossmann 1998, 279, fig. 4

used on such a large scale, which is testament to the unique nature of Philoxenite. There can be no doubt that nearby Alexandria was home to well-trained master builders, who had the knowledge required to design and build Philoxenite in accordance with the theoretical framework of modular design. For example, these experts included Chryses, a *mechanikoi* who was responsible for the construction projects commissioned by Emperor Justinian.³⁶

Secondly, no secular buildings sharing such a uniform design were discovered at various sites associated with Christian pilgrimages dating to the 5th and 6th century CE. This demonstrates that throughout various areas of the Mediterranean a universal architectural approach was not used in the construction of sanctuaries and the associated settlements that served them. Moreover, the similarities in architectural plans are very limited at a regional level. The thermal bath complex at Abū Mīnā, which was copied and duplicated in Philoxenite, is a unique example of this phenomenon. Broadly speaking, there are no further close similarities between these two sites in terms of design method of specific buildings, which is most likely due to the differences in how they were founded. The sanctuary of St Menas developed between the 4th and early 7th centuries CE, as part of many separate investment projects. As a result, the architectural development of the site was far from homogeneous, explaining the irregularity of the town plan. Subsequent construction phases were more organic than coherent and organised, although there is no shortage of straight-line structures in the town.³⁷

Test trenches in Philoxenite indicated that the town was constructed as part of a single, centrally managed construction project. This should have resulted in greater control over the layout of

³⁶ C. Hof even believes that Chryses of Alexandria may have been involved in the planning of the great water cistern at Resafa (Sergiopolis), which was designed using a modular design (see Hof 2019, 234–35). For more information on *mechanikoi* and mathematicians associated with Late Antiquity Alexandria, see McKkenzie 2007, 325–28.

³⁷ It must be noted that the layout of the city was by no means chaotic. The primary consequence of the long development process in Abū Mīnā is that some complexes were based on angled axes and that buildings and rooms were designed as trapezoids. Using such solutions combined different parts of the town which were differently organised. For more information on urban planning in Abū Mīnā, see Grossmann 1990, 40–55.

the settlement, which has been confirmed by archaeological research in the area. This type of project enabled the erection of large and very regular structures which were not restricted by existing buildings and only needed to conform to the general town plan. According to the Encomium of St Menas, the settlement was primarily created to provide accommodation to pilgrims. Pilgrim infrastructure must therefore have constituted the most distinct part of the settlement. This hagiographic text indicates that hospices, rest houses and depositories for clothes and baggage were erected in Philoxenite during the reign of Justinian. From this information, we can assume that some of the modular buildings found at the site were used for this function. We obviously cannot rule out that individual structures may have served multiple purposes, e.g. both as accommodation for pilgrims and as shops.

New urban settlements similar to Philoxenite were a rarity during the Early Byzantine period.³⁸ Furthermore, this case is a testimony of the circumstances and nature of the community that founded the settlement, rooted in the growing importance of pilgrim traffic on the way between Alexandria and the sanctuary of St Menas. Philoxenite's designers were able to satisfy the demand for services generated by these pilgrimages by using efficient modular designs to build infrastructure that served pilgrims on an extensive scale.

References:

Allison, P. M. 2001. "Using the material and written sources: turn of the millennium approaches to Roman domestic space." *AJA* 105, no. 2: 181–208.

Augenti, A. 2011. "Classe: archeologia di una città scomparsa." In *Classe: indagini sul potenziale archeologico di una città scomparsa*, ed. A. Augenti, 15–44. Bologna: Ante Quem.

³⁸ For one of the more recent articles on Christian cities of the Early Byzantine period, see Blömer 2021, 205–19.

- Augenti, A., and E. Cirelli. 2012. "From suburb to port: the rise (and fall) of Classe as a centre of trade and redistribution." In *Rome, Portus and the Mediterranean*, ed. S. Keay, 205–21. Archaeological Monographs of the British School at Rome 21. London: British School at Rome.
- Babraj, K., A. Drzymuchowska, and N. Willburger. 2014. "Marea 2011." *Polish Archaeology in the Mediterranean* 23/1: 45–61.
- Babraj, K., and H. Szymańska. 2008. "Sāqiyah." In *Marea, vol. I. Byzantine Marea: Excavations in 2000–2003 and 2006*, ed. H. Szymańska and K. Babraj, 85–101. Biblioteka Muzeum Archeologicznego w Krakowie 4. Kraków: Muzeum Archeologiczne w Krakowie.
- Blömer, M. 2021. "Sacred spaces and new cities in the Byzantine East." In *Urban Religion in Late Antiquity*, ed. A. Lätzer-Lasar and E. Rubens Urciuoli, 205–24. Religionsgeschichtliche Versuche und Vorarbeiten 76. Berlin and Boston: De Gruyter.
- Butler, H. C. 1920. *Syria: Publications of the Princeton University Archaeological Expeditions to Syria in 1904–5 and 1909. Division II: Architecture, Section B: Northern Syria*. Leiden: E.J. Brill.
- Chen, D. 1990. "On planning of synagogues and churches in Palaestina: a comparison with Syria and Illyricum." In *Christian Archaeology in the Holy Land, New discoveries: Essays in Honour of Virgilio C. Corbo, OFM*, ed. G. C. Bottini, L. Di Segni, and E. Alliata, 523–33. Studium Biblicum Franciscanum. Collectio Maior 36. Jerusalem: Franciscan Printing Press.
- Christern, J. 1976. *Das frühchristliche Pilgerheiligtum von Tebessa: Architektur und Ornamentik einer spätantiken Bauhütte in Nordafrika*. Wiesbaden: Steiner.
- Crow, J. 2020. "'Still waters run deep': cisterns and the hydraulic infrastructure of Constantinople and Alexandria." *Antiquité Tardive* 28: 113–25.

- Davison, D.P. 1989. *The Barracks of the Roman Army from the 1st to 3rd Century A.D. A Comparative Study of the Barracks from Fortresses, Forts and Fortlets with an Analysis of Building Types and Construction, Stabling and Garrisons*. BAR International Series 472(i–iii). Oxford: B.A.R.
- de Ruyt, C. 1983. *Macellum: marche alimentaire des romains*. Publications d’histoire de l’Art et d’Archeologie de l’Universite Catholique de Louvain 35. Louvain-la-Neuve: Institut Superieur d’Archeologie et d’Histoire de l’Art.
- Derda, T. 2020. “‘Marea’ ad Aegyptum: new research and new documents.” In *Crossing time and space: to commemorate Hanna Szymanska*, ed. K. Myśliwiec and A. Ryś, 61–74. Warsaw and Wiesbaden: IKŚiO PAN; Harrassowitz Verlag.
- Derda, T., M. Gwiazda, T. Barański, A. Pawlikowska-Gwiazda, and D. F. Wieczorek. 2020. “Excavations in the northern and eastern parts of the Byzantine town at Marea.” *Polish Archaeology in the Mediterranean* 29/2: 551–75.
- Derda, T., M. Gwiazda, K. Misiewicz, and W. Małkowski. 2021. “Marea/Northern Hawwariya in Northern Egypt: integrated results of non-invasive and excavation works.” *Archaeological Prospection* 28, no. 2: 123–36.
- Derda, T., M. Gwiazda, and A. Pawlikowska-Gwiazda. 2020. “Development of a settlement on the northeastern promontory at ‘Marea.’” *Polish Archaeology in the Mediterranean* 29/2: 531–50.
- Döring, M. 2007. “Römische Aquädukte und Großzisternen der Phlegräischen Felder.” In *Antike Zisternen*, ed. C. P. J. Ohlig, 1–87. Schriften der Deutschen Wasserhistorischen Gesellschaft 9. Siegburg: DWhG.
- Drescher, J., ed. 1946. *Apa Mena: a Selection of Coptic Texts Relating to St. Menas*. Publications de la Société d’archéologie copte. Textes et Documents 6. Le Caire: Institut français d’archéologie orientale.

- Ellis, S. J. R. 2018. *The Roman Retail Revolution: the Socio-Economic World of the Taberna*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Fournet, T., and B. Redon. 2017. "Romano-Byzantine baths of Egypt: the birth and spread of a little-known regional model." In *Collective Baths in Egypt 2: new discoveries and perspectives*, ed. B. Redon, 279–321. Cairo: Institut français d'archéologie orientale.
- Grossmann, P. 1990. "On the urbanistic arrangements in Abu Mina." *Egyptian Society of Greek and Roman Studies* 1: 40–55.
- Grossmann, P. 1998. "Abū Mīnā." In *Ägypten in spätantik-christlicher Zeit: Einführung in die koptische Kultur*, ed. M. F. Krause. Sprachen und Kulturen des christlichen Orients 4. Wiesbaden: Reichert.
- Grossmann, P. 2004. "Report on the Excavations at Abū Mīnā in Spring 2003." *Bulletin de la Société d'archéologie copte* 43: 33–43.
- Grossmann, P., and J. Kościuk. 2005. "Report on the excavations at Abū Mīnā in Spring 2005." *Bulletin de la Société d'archéologie copte* 44: 29–44.
- Gwiazda, M., and T. Derda. 2021. "Marea: a swan song of ancient urban planning." *Antiquity* 95, no. 382. <https://doi.org/10.15184/aqy.2021.88>.
- Gwiazda, M., and D. Wielgosz-Rondolino. 2019. "'Marea' on Lake Mareotis: a Roman amphorae dump, a Byzantine period house, and its Early Islamic dwellers." *JEA* 105, no. 2: 259–73.
- Haggag, M. 2010. "The city of Marea/Philoxenité: reflections on the Alexandria University excavations, 1977–1981." In *Lake Mareotis: Reconstructing the Past. Proceedings of the International Conference on the Archaeology of the Mareotic Region Held at Alexandria University, Egypt, 5th–6th April 2008*, ed. L. Blue and E. Khalil, 47–56. BAR International Series 2113. Oxford: Archaeopress.

- Hof, C. 2019. "The monumental Late Antique cisterns of Resafa, Syria as refined capacity and water-quality regulation system." In *Size Matters: Understanding Monumentality Across Ancient Civilizations*, ed. F Buccellati, S. Hageneuer, S. Van der Heyden, and F. Levenson, 223–39. Bielefeld: Transcript.
- Husselman, E.M. 1979. *Karanis Excavations of the University of Michigan in Egypt 1928–1935: Topography and Architecture. A Summary of the Reports of the Director, Enoch E. Peterson*. The Kelsey Museum of Archaeology Studies 5. Ann Arbor: The University of Michigan Press.
- Junecke, H. 1983. *Proportionen frühchristlicher Basiliken des Balkan im Vergleich von zwei unterschiedlichen Meßverfahren: Proportionen der Hagia Sophia in Istanbul*. Tübingen: Wasmuth.
- Kingsley, S. A. 2004. *Barbarian Seas: Late Rome to Islam*. London: Periplus.
- Klemm, R., and D. D. Klemm. 1992. *Steine und Steinbrüche im Alten Ägypten*. Berlin: Springer.
- Kościuk, J. 2012. "Preliminary observations on Late Antique Marea topography." In *Nie tylko trony: księga jubileuszowa ofiarowana Profesorowi Ernestowi Niemczykowi*, ed. J. L. Dobesz, A. Gryglewska, and M. M. Rudnicka-Bogusz, 29–38. Wrocław: Oficyna Wydawnicza Politechniki Wrocławskiej.
- Kristensen, T. M. 2017. "Excavating Meriamlik: sacred space and economy in Late Antique pilgrimage." In *Excavating Pilgrimage: Archaeological Approaches to Sacred Travel and Movement in the Ancient World*, ed. T. M. Kristensen and W. Friese, 224–44. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Lavan, L. 2020. *Public Space in the Late Antique City, vol. I. Streets, Processions, Fora, Agorai, Macellae, Shops*. Late Antique Archaeology. Supplementary Series 5.1. Leiden and Boston: Brill.

- Maiuri, A. 1934. *I campi Flegrei dal sepolcro di Virgilio all'antro di Cuma*. Itinerari dei musei e monumenti d'Italia 32. Roma: La Libreria dello Stato.
- McKenzie, J. 2007. *The Architecture of Alexandria and Egypt: c. 300 B.C. to A.D. 700*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Milson, D. 2007. *Art and Architecture of the Synagogue in Late Antique Palestine: in the Shadow of the Church*. Ancient Judaism and Early Christianity 65. Leiden and Boston: Brill.
- Müller-Wiener, W. 1966. "Abu Mena: 4. Vorläufiger Bericht." *MDIK* 21: 171–87.
- Oleson, J.P. 2017. "The modular planning of Roman fortifications in the Near East: principles and process." In *The Socio-Economic History and Material Culture of the Roman and Byzantine Near East: Essays in Honor of S. Thomas Parker*, ed. W.D. Ward, 237–272. Piscataway NJ: Gorgias Press.
- Ousterhout, R. G. 1999. *Master Builders of Byzantium*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Papaconstantinou, A. 2007. "Divine or human? Some remarks on the design and layout of late antique basilicas." In *The Material and the Ideal: Essays in Medieval Art and Archaeology in Honour of Jean-Michel Spieser*, ed. A. Cutler and A. Papaconstantinou, 31–46. *Medieval Mediterranean* 70. Leiden and Boston: Brill.
- Patrich, J. 1996. "Warehouses and granaries in Caesarea Maritima." In *Caesarea Maritima: a Retrospective after Two Millennia*, ed. A. Raban and K. G. Holum, 146–76. *Documenta et Monumenta Orientis Antiqui* 21. Leiden: Brill.
- Petruso, K., and C. Gabel. 1982. *Marea: a Byzantine Port in Northern Egypt*. Boston: African Studies Center, Boston University.
- Pieri, D. 2009. "Saint-Syméon-le-Stylite (Syrie du Nord): les bâtiments d'accueil et les boutiques à l'entrée du sanctuaire (note d'information)." *CRAI* 153, no. 4: 1393–1420.

- Prentice, W. K. 1922. *Syria: Publications of the Princeton University Archaeological Expeditions to Syria in 1904–5 and 1909. Division III, Section B. Northern Syria: Greek and Latin inscriptions*. Leiden: E.J. Brill.
- Rickman, G. 1971. *Roman Granaries and Store Buildings*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Rodziewicz, M. 1984. *Les habitations romaines tardives d'Alexandrie: à la lumière des fouilles polonaises à Kôm el-Dikka*. Alexandrie 3. Varsovie: Éditions Scientifiques de Pologne.
- Sadek, M. 1992. "The Baths at the Ancient Harbour of Marea." In *Sesto Congresso internazionale di egittologia: atti, vol. I*, 549–54. Turin: International Association of Egyptologists.
- Spremo-Petrović, N. 1971. *Proportions architecturales dans les plans des basiliques de la préfecture de l'Illyricum*. Beograd: Institut Archéologique.
- Stewart, C. A. 2016. "The modular design of Early Byzantine cisterns and reservoirs." In *Against Gravity: Building Practices in the Pre-industrial world*, ed. R. Ousterhout, D. Borbonus, and E. Dumser. <https://www.sas.upenn.edu/ancient/masons/abstracts/Agudo/Stewart - Byzantine Reservoirs Against Gravity STEWART 2015 - FINAL Merged.pdf>.
- Szymańska, H., and K. Babraj, eds. 2008. *Marea, vol. I. Byzantine Marea: Excavations in 2000–2003 and 2006*. Biblioteka Muzeum Archeologicznego w Krakowie 4. Kraków: Muzeum Archeologiczne w Krakowie.
- Tchalenko, G. 1953. *Villages antiques de la Syrie du Nord: le massif du Bélus à l'époque romaine, vol. I*. Bibliothèque archéologique et historique 50. Paris: P. Geuthner.
- Wilkinson, J. 1981. "Architectural procedures in Byzantine Palestine." *Levant* 13, no. 1: 156–72.
- Wilkinson, J. 1984. "What Butler saw." *Levant* 16, no. 1: 113–27.

Zanini, E. 2007. "Technology and ideas: architects and master-builders in the Early Byzantine world." In *Technology in Transition: A.D. 300–650*, ed. L. Lavan, E. Zanini, and A. C. Sarantis, 379–405. *Late Antique Archaeology 4*. Leiden and Boston: Brill.

Caption

1. Plan of Philoxenite with locations of the buildings mentioned in the text (Courtesy of the Polish Center of Mediterranean Archaeology, drawing)
2. Orthophoto map of building S3 (Courtesy of the Polish Center of Mediterranean Archaeology, drawing)
3. Orthophoto map of buildings in area W5 and W1 (Courtesy of the Polish Center of Mediterranean Archaeology, orthophoto and drawing)
4. a) Orthophoto map of building W2. b) Orthophoto map of bath complex T2 (Courtesy of the Polish Center of Mediterranean Archaeology, orthophotos and drawings)
5. Orthophoto map of building DD1 (Courtesy of the Polish Center of Mediterranean Archaeology, orthophotos and drawings)
6. Examples of Roman and Early Byzantine modular buildings from different parts of the Mediterranean
 - a) Cellular shops at Abū Mīnā (after Grossmann 2004, fig. 1, with modifications)
 - b) Macellum at Puteoli (after Maiuri 1934, 29, fig. 13, with modifications)
 - c) Modular cistern at Loutron, Salamis (Constantia) (after Stewart 2015, fig. 4.c, with modifications)
 - d) Inns at Deir Seman (after Butler 1920, fig. 284, with modifications)

e) Pilgrims' hostel at Tebessa (after Christern 1976, fig. 21, with *** modifications)

■ - MODULE BUILDINGS

DD1

W4

T2

W2

W5-C

W5-B

W5-A

W1-C

W1-B

ST2

W1-A

S3

0 200 M

0

50 M

CHANNEL

0 30 M

